

Issue 02 2025

PHENET

PHENOTYPING & ENVIROTYPING
SOLUTIONS FOR AGROECOLOGY

In this newsletter...

PHENET At The EPPS25 – learn more about how PHENET stood out at EPPS25.

Use-case spotlight – new advances in wheat disease detection and climate-driven shifts in fungal behaviour.

Upcoming PHENET events – Join us at upcoming events across Europe

NEWSLETTER PHENET

What's New in PHENET:
Innovations, Collaborations, and Impact!

Welcome to the 2nd PHENET Newsletter!

As PHENET enters the second half of its journey, 2025 marks a key turning point: several of our phenotyping and envirotyping technologies are moving from prototypes to validated solutions, ready to evolve into future European services. This reflects the core ambition of Horizon Europe INFRA-TECH projects to innovate and identify robust, scalable tools that can ultimately be operated by the European Research Infrastructures (RI) [EMPHASIS](#), [AnaEE](#), [eLTER](#), and [ELIXIR](#).

Our strong presence at the European Plant Phenotyping Symposium ([EPPS25](#)) in Bonn and the positive feedback on the technologies showcased at the PHENET booth highlight growing momentum. Interactions with breeders, SMEs and researchers confirmed rising interest in interoperable, field-ready phenotyping solutions. New videos from several use-cases show our technologies being tested across species and cropping systems, while progress continues, turning these developments into candidate RI services.

PHENET continues to build and mobilise the scientific and community impact through publications, talks, industrial collaboration, [ELIXIR](#) training, the Biohackathon and the engagement of early-career researchers via the [International Plant Phenotyping Network - Early Career Professional Network \(IPPN-ECPN\)](#).

This newsletter also brings updates from our partner RIs and related projects such as [Microbes4Climate](#) and [AgroServ](#), whose policy developments will shape the landscape into which our PHENET results will be integrated

As we enter year 4, our focus is to consolidate the most promising outputs and bring them closer to transnational access and long-term service delivery. PHENET has built strong momentum; now we accelerate.

— Bertrand Muller, PHENET coordinator

PHENET At The EPPS25

PHENET had a strong and prominent presence at the European Plant Phenomics Symposium (EPPS2025) in Bonn from 16-19 September. With over 350 participants and a rich scientific program, the event was an excellent opportunity to showcase the work of PHENET.

The PHENET booth drew considerable interest and helped highlight our technologies, services, and achievements. This was reflected in post-event engagement:

Policy brief views increased from 400 to over 500 (with 174 downloads), newsletter engagement rose by more than 35%, and LinkedIn outreach grew by 7%. Webinar recordings and Coffee Session videos also attracted steady attention.

Overall, PHENET's presence at EPPS25 underscored its growing scientific impact and its central role in supporting innovation and collaboration in plant phenotyping.

Read the article on PHENET at the EPPS in the [GEVES newsletter of November 2025](#)

Keynotes

AI-based phenotyping
Smart Data for Smart Crops

Posters

14 contributions from PHENET partners

Training School

Co-organised programme training with 30 participants

IPPN-ECP Network

PHENET members supported the kick-off meeting

JXB Special Issue

Plant Phenomics and Enviromics Across Scales - abstracts open until 31 March 2026

Use-Case Spotlight

Advances in Detecting *Fusarium* Head Blight in Winter Wheat

Reducing the risk of mycotoxin production caused by *Fusarium* head blight (FHB) remains a major challenge in winter wheat production. Today, FHB severity is still assessed visually in the field, which requires expert knowledge and is highly time-consuming. Within PHENET's Plant Health Use Case (UC1), partners are developing imaging-based methods and portable tools to support (and eventually replace) visual scoring.

The study evaluates three approaches:

- High-resolution images collected in the field were used to train deep learning models, which successfully classified FHB resistance and can serve as a reliable alternative to visual scoring.
- NIR hyperspectral imaging tested under real field conditions to distinguish FHB from Take-all. While effective for assessing overall ear health, current models cannot yet reliably differentiate the two diseases.
- FluorPen measurements were able to detect high infection levels and distinguish resistant varieties; however, they were less reliable for low-level infections and limited by the need for dark adaptation.

This research highlights the potential of **AI-based imaging** and advanced sensors to make FHB resistance assessment faster, more objective and scalable for breeding and variety evaluation.

These findings were presented at EPPS25, CIMA 2025, and in a thesis defence, with publications forthcoming.

Read the full report at our Zenodo community:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17658135>

Seydina Kone

Damien Vincke

Simon Treier

When Fungi Change Roles: The Secret Response of Fungi to a Warming World

In heathland ecosystems, ericoid mycorrhizal (ERM) fungi support plant growth by unlocking nutrients from organic matter. This study investigates whether climate change could push these fungi to behave more like decomposers, altering soil carbon storage.

Using the ECOTRON facility at Hasselt University, Vera Claessens, with Prof. Nadia Soudzilovskaia, in the PHENET Use Case Root Phenology track how carbon flows between plants, fungi, and soil under different climate scenarios. With PHENET support, this project also demonstrates how stable isotope probing (SIP) can be used in ECOTRONS as a shared service for ecosystem research.

For more information, contact: vera.claessens@uhasselt.be

Bags filled with labelled plant material were placed in the soil to track decomposition.

Labelled CO₂ was prepared in a gas cylinder, loaded into syringes, and injected into the ecosystem atmosphere twice daily for five days.

Use Case Videos Now Available

At the EPPS25 PHENET booth, visitors could watch a selection of short use-case videos showcasing the technologies, methods, and services being developed across the consortium. These videos highlight the diversity of PHENET's scientific work, from plant health monitoring to soil processes, climate responses, AI in phenotyping, and large-scale data integration.

These use-case videos are now published and available online for the broader community. They serve as accessible introductions to PHENET's research activities and will be expanded with additional content over time.

The full collection is available on our Zenodo community page at [10.5281/zenodo.17789759](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.17789759).

Watch the videos [here](#)

News from PHENET Partners

PhenOrchards: HIPHEN Delivers a Major Step Forward in Orchard Phenotyping

As a proud partner of PHENET, HIPHEN has developed PhenOrchards – a tailor-made, orchard-built phenotyping system designed specifically to meet the project's research needs.

This innovative solution enables non-destructive, high-resolution data collection in orchards, which advanced algorithms developed by HIPHEN convert into precise plant traits. The result is a powerful combination of cutting-edge hardware, robotics, and AI-driven data processing, delivering deeper insights for plant breeding, agroecological research, and sustainable agriculture. A big thank you to all PHENET partners for their collaboration on this journey toward data-driven breeding from phenotypic data.

Watch PhenOrchards in action and see how we are turning raw data into actionable plant traits: <https://youtu.be/PPjyMF0E0Ng>

Building the Future PHENET Service Portfolio

PHENET Partner and leading RI has completed the initial phase of identifying and describing candidate services, which represents an important milestone for the project. PHENET is now ready to move forward to the next stage, engaging with relevant RIs to further evaluate their services, explore their feasibility, and seek potential endorsement.

This process will support the transfer of selected services towards long-term adoption and sustainability within the phenotyping community.

For questions, contact Thi Ly Mai: ly.mai@anaee.eu

Meet the Research Infrastructures in PHENET: eLTER Advancing Towards ERIC

In this issue, we feature eLTER and highlight a major milestone on the path to becoming an ERIC

eLTER has submitted its Step-1 Application to the European Commission to establish eLTER as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). This marks a major milestone toward securing a long-term, pan-European legal framework for ecosystem research.

For more details, visit the [website](#)

The submission, coordinated by Germany as the hosting country, includes the draft statutes, scientific and technical description, and letters of support required for ERIC evaluation. Once approved and followed by Step-2, eLTER will gain a stable legal and operational structure, strengthening collaboration across its extensive network of ecosystem and socio-ecological research sites. This development is highly relevant for the wider European RI landscape, highlighting continued progress toward sustainable, integrated research infrastructures.

Scaling Carbon Removal: Integrating Nature-Based and Technological Solutions for Climate Neutrality

eLTER Publishes First Policy Brief on Carbon Removal

The first policy brief from eLTER, “Scaling Carbon Removal: Integrating Nature-Based and Technological Solutions for Climate Neutrality”, highlights that carbon emission reductions alone will not achieve Europe’s climate goals and calls for a rapid scale-up of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) efforts. It emphasises combining nature-based approaches like forests, soils, and peatlands with emerging technological solutions, supported by clear policies, consistent measurement standards, and collaboration across science, policy, and industry. As a major environmental research infrastructure, eLTER offers the long-term data and monitoring capacity needed to support and verify effective CDR strategies.

Scan this code and learn more about this policy

Read the full brief on the eLTER website <https://elter-ri.eu/news> and subscribe to [eLTER Newsletter](#)

Community Engagement

Easy & Quick – Visualising NGS Count Data with Python at EPPS 2025

The hands-on workshop "Easy & Quick – Visualising NGS Count Data with Python," at EPPS 2025, organised by Anna-Maria Möller and Daniela Dey (West German Genome Center), together with Sebastian Beier and Daniel Wibberg (Forschungszentrum Jülich, de.NBI & ELIXIR-DE, and PHENET members), was aimed at researchers with little or no coding experience. The workshop offered 12 participants an accessible and supportive environment to develop Python skills central to modern bioinformatics workflows.

Participants were introduced to the essentials of Python programming, data handling, and visualisation, all within the JupyterLab environment of the Galaxy Hub. The session began with a brief overview of NGS transcriptomics data and its significance, setting the stage for a series of focused, interactive exercises.

Attendees practised loading, inspecting, and manipulating real count data sets using pandas, moving seamlessly into basic statistics and the creation of informative histograms to explore count distributions.

The highlight for many was the use of seaborn and matplotlib to generate publication-quality plots. The session concluded with a discussion on how these foundational data skills build towards more advanced tasks, such as normalisation and principal component analysis (PCA), leaving participants well-prepared for their own transcriptomic analyses.

Overall, this workshop provided practical, hands-on experience that demystified Python for newcomers and helped bridge the gap to more complex analyses. Its success reflects the commitment of PHENET to high-quality and inclusive training.

For more information, contact Daniel Wibberg (dwibberg@cebitec.uni-bielefeld.de)

PHENET Research Presented at CIMA 2025

Seydina Koné (GEVES) presented PHENET research at the VÉGÉPHYLL – 14ème Conférence Internationale sur les Maladies des Plantes, held on 2–4 December 2025 in Angers, France, in collaboration with CRA-W and Agroscope.

The talk, titled “Resistance assessment of wheat varieties against *Fusarium* Head Blight using artificial intelligence on RGB images”, highlighted advances in AI-based phenotyping for improved disease resistance evaluation.

This work reflects ongoing efforts within PHENET to apply image analysis and machine learning to plant health challenges.

PHENET members are invited to join the team!

Scan this code to watch the entire interview

Interview with Prof. Jennifer Clarke

During the last General Assembly meeting in Lisbon, Portugal, we had the pleasure of interviewing Prof. Jennifer Clarke (University of Nebraska–Lincoln), Chair of the International Plant Phenotyping Network (IPPN) and member of the PHENET Scientific Advisory Board. In a series of short video segments, she shares her insights on the strengths of plant phenotyping research across Europe and North America, the future role of AI in phenomics, opportunities for transatlantic collaboration, and the contributions of phenotyping and envirotyping to agroecology.

The interview offers a forward-looking perspective on PHENET’s mission and the evolving needs of the community.

AnaEE TechUp!

Stay updated on new ecosystem research technologies, upcoming webinars on the AnaEE website at <https://www.anaee.eu>, and watch past sessions on [YouTube](#).

Save The Date

AnaEE Science Conference, 29 Sept–1 Oct 2026, Menton. Submissions open January 2026.

From Our Community To PHENET

PHENET at the 4th BioHackathon Germany

The 4th BioHackathon Germany (1–5 December 2025, Kassel) brought together more than 175 participants to collaborate on 11 interdisciplinary projects in life science and bioinformatics.

The PHENET-based project “Implementing AI in Meta-analysis: Can domain-specific paper selection and data extraction be done effectively?” was part of the event. The team explored how AI can extract structured data from scientific PDFs, a key step in meta-analysis. Early results showed strong potential, especially for figures and tables, though complex publication formats still challenge current models. Improved prompting helped increase accuracy.

The project team will continue to refine extraction workflows, develop user-friendly interfaces, and apply their approach in future meta-analyses, reflecting the innovative and collaborative spirit of the BioHackathon.

For more information, contact Daniel Wibberg
dwibberg@cebitec.uni-bielefeld.de

AI-Driven Meta-Analysis Featured at the 4th Biohackathon

Madhuri Paul presented the project “Implementing AI in Meta-Analysis: Can Domain-Specific Paper Selection and Data Extraction Be Done Effectively?” at the 4th Biohackathon Germany.

The contribution explored how large machine learning models can support and enhance meta-analysis workflows, particularly in automating paper selection and data extraction for domain-specific studies.

The project is open for collaboration, and interested PHENET members are invited to join the team!

Phenomics

November 28th ,15:00-16:00 CET

Webinars

2025

Presented by

AI-Powered Phenomics: Transforming Crop Science for a Climate-Resilient Future

Dr. Michael Gomez Selvaraj
Crop Physiologist \Digital Agriculture - Alliance
Bioversity & CIAT

PhenomicsWebinars Return for 2025/26 with Season 4

The IPPN Working Group Applications of AI in Plant Phenotyping is relaunching the popular PhenomicsWebinars, running monthly from late Winter 2025 to Spring 2026. Hosted by Prof. Arti Singh (Iowa State University) and Germano Gomez (VIB), the series will explore the latest advances in AI-driven plant phenotyping.

Kickoff Episode: Dr. Michael Gomez Selvaraj

Mark your calendars! The season kicks off on November 28, 2025, at 15:00 CET, with Dr. Michael Gomez Selvaraj from the Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT. Dr. Selvaraj will present on “AI-Powered Phenomics: Transforming Crop Science for a Climate-Resilient Future.”

This is a live webinar event, providing a direct opportunity for attendees to engage with the speaker during a dedicated Q&A session.

Don't miss out on these essential, state-of-the-art insights!

Click [here](#) for more information

PHENET Link to EOSC Strengthened!

Congratulations to Jessica Lindvall on her election to the EOSC Association Board of Directors!

We are pleased to share that Jessica has been elected to the Board of Directors of the EOSC Association, marking an important milestone and strengthening the connection between PHENET and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

EOSC plays a key role in shaping Europe's open science and data ecosystem, and this election further reinforces the alignment of PHENET with EOSC principles and objectives, as already outlined in the PHENET proposal. This development is particularly relevant for policy, funding, and governmental stakeholders interested in data interoperability, FAIR data, and sustainable research infrastructures.

We warmly congratulate Jessica on this achievement and look forward to continued synergies between PHENET, EOSC, and the broader research infrastructure landscape.

Click [here](#) for more information.

Elected to a 1-year term

Jessica Lindvall Stockholm University

- ▶ Associate Professor in Bioinformatics at Stockholm University
- ▶ 10 years of expertise in research infrastructure sector with a focus on people infrastructure, lifelong learning, team science and governance

"I am a strong advocate of Open Science and FAIR principles. I believe that EOSC is the key player in making the transition to Open Science happen in Europe."

- Deputy Head of Node ELIXIR-SE, the **Swedish National Research Infrastructure in Bioinformatics (NBIS)**, responsible for strategic engagements and capacity building
- Executive Committee member of the **ELIXIR Training Platform**
- Head of Training at **LifeScienceLab** Training Hub, setting up operational procedures to ensure high-quality and FAIR training across thematic domains
- Chair of the national research infrastructure **ArchLab** Steering Board
- Served as a co-chair of the [Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC](#) Task Force (2021-2023) and is currently engaged in the EOSC Opportunity Area 5: [Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling](#)

Opportunities to Access Research Facilities: Transnational and Virtual Access (TNA/VA)

AgroServ

Stay Tuned for AgroServ 5th Call!

AgroServ is a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Union.

AgroServ has concluded the **4th Transnational and Virtual Access Call (TNA/VA)** with 48 applications. Currently, feasible projects are under scientific evaluation.

AgroServ calls offer free TNA/VA access to more than 143 cutting-edge research services in the transdisciplinary field of agroecology — available to researchers, industry professionals, and practitioners worldwide.

The 5th TNA/VA call is anticipated in early 2026, with new updates in the eligibility criteria that will streamline the application requirements

Register for the next AgroServ Connect webinar <https://bit.ly/AgroServConnect5>

18 December 2025

A spotlight on the experience of a successful TNA user, providing practical insights on how to design and implement an access project.

What can be achieved through AgroServ access?

Watch a short video interview following one user's journey using biostimulants to improve plant stress resilience under climate change youtube.com/watch?v=1j3qVIU692U

Questions?

Daniele Baldo daniele.baldo@anaee.eu
Heba Ibrahim: h.ibrahim@fz-juelich.de

Microbes4Climate

Microbes4Climate – 2nd TNA Call!

Launch: 09 December 2025

Microbes4Climate is a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Union.

The 1st TNA Call has recently closed with positive results (26 submitted proposals from 20 European and non-European countries).

The first call indicated strong engagement from the scientific community in exploring microbial-driven solutions for climate-related challenges.

Looking ahead, the 2nd TNA Call will expand opportunities for researchers to access M4C's infrastructures and expertise.

The Catalogue of Services includes access to 140+ services, including :

- Unique microbial collections
- Advanced laboratories and instruments
- Support for biodiversity, biotechnology, and environmental applications
- Physical, remote, and virtual access

Learn more and apply now!

<https://microbes4climate.eu/tna>

If you have any questions, contact:

accessofficer@microbes4climate.eu

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Our LinkedIn Page

Our Zenodo Community

Thank you to all contributors and partners!
Stay tuned for our 3rd issue contributions: June 2026!

Have a question?
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